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D9.1 - Launch dedicated website and social media

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R	Document, report	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU	Public	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	<input type="checkbox"/>	CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	<input type="checkbox"/>
DEC	Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.	<input type="checkbox"/>			
OTHER		<input type="checkbox"/>			

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1 Executive summary

This report describes the work carried out by the University of York and SQ Consult with regards to Task 9.1 (launch dedicated website and social media) of the CHAMPION project. The CHAMPION website and social media are channels which allow for a quick and broad distribution and exchange of information on the progress of the project to interested parties, stakeholders and the public.

2 Website

A dedicated project website for CHAMPION www.champion-project.eu was officially launched on 26 August 2020, containing the main sections and information that will be further elaborated (Figure 1). The project management and communication teams presented a preliminary website for CHAMPION (Figure 2) to the consortium at the project’s kick-off meeting (held virtually on 25-26 June 2020). The aim of this was to gather feedback from all partners on the draft design and basic content before going forward. Furthermore, as the project logo had not yet been designed at this stage, it could not yet be included in the website and the colour scheme would need to be updated to match the logo.

Figure 1. CHAMPION website homepage screenshot

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Figure 2. Preliminary website screenshot

2.1 Platform

The CHAMPION website was created within the well-established [Wix platform](#). This guarantees a long-term availability of up-to-date features that can be accessed without any hurdles. It is user-friendly and receives lots of updates and technical support from a big international community of users and programmers. Furthermore, it fulfils the security as well as EU data protection requirements and offers flexible components to modify navigation as well as content quickly, securely and easily. The URL www.champion-project.eu is owned by SQ Consult.

2.2 Structure and design

The initial structure of the external website is as follows:

- Home
- Objectives - www.champion-project.eu/objectives
- Partners - www.champion-project.eu/partners
- Work areas (content coming soon) - www.champion-project.eu/work-areas
- Deliverables (public deliverables will be added to this page when available) - www.champion-project.eu/deliverables
- News - www.champion-project.eu/news
- Contact - www.champion-project.eu/contact

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The final website design developed by the University of York corresponds to the CHAMPION logo. Suggestions for the logo were put forward by partners and external graphic designers in time for the project kick-off meeting, and the final version was developed by Delight Design following feedback by the consortium by the end of August 2020.

Figure 3. News page of the website showing the latest news stories relating to the project

2.3 Privacy policy and cookies

In addition to the above pages which are visible in the navigation bar, there is also a GDPR compliant Privacy Policy page which includes information on the specific cookies in use on the website and personal data collected for analytics purposes. When visiting the site for the first time, a “cookie alert” banner (Figure 4) appears requiring the user to accept cookies or amend their cookie settings. This banner also links to the Privacy Policy page.

We use cookies and similar technologies to enable services and functionality on our site and to understand your interaction with our service. By clicking on accept, you agree to our use of such technologies for marketing and analytics. [See Privacy Policy](#)

Cookie Settings

Accept

Figure 4. Cookie alert banner

2.4 Maintenance and Updating

The University of York are the owners of the Wix account and administer the website, analysing the web traffic periodically through Google Analytics, in order to measure how users interact with the website content. A dedicated staff member is updating the website regularly, sharing news, information on events, presentations and relevant studies.

3 Social Media

In addition to the website, dedicated social media channels for the CHAMPION project have been created on [LinkedIn](#), [Facebook](#) and [Twitter](#). These are important tools to reach out to, and inform stakeholders on the progress of the project and were launched in June 2020 in time for the kick-off meeting. The initial design of the social media profiles was updated to include the project logo when this was finalised in August. Throughout the project relevant topics that are trending social media will be identified and connected to a consortium expert that can post added value to the online discussions. Social media are regularly monitored and updated by a dedicated staff member, with news, web streaming, pictures, events etc. Links to Facebook, LinkedIn and Twitter have been included in the CHAMPION webpage.

Figure 5. Social media profiles – LinkedIn (top left), Twitter (top right) and Facebook (bottom)

4 Conclusions

The CHAMPION website was delivered in two stages, with an initial design used to provide basic project information and gather feedback whilst the full version was being developed. The final design was launched in conjunction with the official logo within the first 3 months of the project, as scheduled. The website will be maintained and updated regularly throughout the life of the project. Additional areas can be added as necessary to ensure it remains relevant to the needs of the project and stakeholders.

In addition to the website, dedicated social media channels for the CHAMPION project have been created on LinkedIn, Facebook and Twitter. The website and social media channels will support the effective communication within the project and with external parties, such as the general public and stakeholders.